

A NEW EQUIVALENT CONSTANT *R*-RATIO LOADING APPROACH FOR PREDICTING FATIGUE LIFE OF CFRP LAMINATES UNDER VARIABLE LOADING

M. Kawai¹ and D. Sango²

¹ Department of Engineering Mechanics and Energy, University of Tsukuba
Tsukuba, Ibaraki 305-8573, Japan; mkawai@kz.tsukuba.ac.jp

² Department of Engineering Mechanics and Energy, University of Tsukuba
Tsukuba, Ibaraki 305-8573, Japan; s1420895@u.tsukuba.ac.jp

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ABSTRACT

A waveform based methodology for prediction of variable loading fatigue life of composites is developed. The variable *R*-ratio fatigue tests in which the stress ratio of fatigue loading alternates between two specified values with different stress levels that correspond to the same number of cycles to failure are first reviewed. The prediction of fatigue life using the Miner rule is excessively optimistic for alternating *R*-ratio loading, while it is satisfactory in the case of alternation of fatigue waveforms of different magnitudes at a constant stress ratio. On the basis of these observations, a variable maximum stress loading at a constant stress ratio that is equivalent to a given alternating *R*-ratio loading is identified. It turns out that fatigue life can be predicted for any given alternating *R*-ratio loading by applying the Miner rule to the equivalent constant stress ratio waveform identified. In order to evaluate this idea, fatigue tests are performed for the variable maximum stress loading waveforms at a constant stress ratio that are equivalent to the alternating *R*-ratio loading waveforms examined in the previous study. A good correlation between the predicted and experimental fatigue lives suggests that the use of the concept of an equivalent single *R*-ratio waveform in conjunction with the anisomorphic constant fatigue life diagram approach provides a potentially useful tool for prediction of variable loading fatigue life of composites.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fatigue loading that structural components made of carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRPs) undergo during service is not constant amplitude cyclic loading, but variable cyclic loading in general. For reliable application of CFRPs to the key components of structures in rapidly growing application areas, therefore, it is a prerequisite to establish a method for accurately and efficiently evaluating their fatigue lives under variable loading conditions [1, 2]. This prerequisite involves two main issues to be coped with. One issue is the establishment of an engineering tool by which the fatigue life of CFRPs under constant amplitude loading can be predicted for any constant stress ratio as well as at any constant stress level. The other issue is the establishment of an engineering methodology by which the fatigue life of CFRPs can be predicted for any sequence of waveforms of different stress ratios as well as of different stress levels.

The first problem mentioned above has successfully been solved by means of the anisomorphic constant fatigue life diagram approach [3, 4]. In contrast, the second problem of variable loading fatigue has not yet fully been solved. To deal with the second problem, we need to understand not only the effect of variation in alternating stress amplitude, but also the effect of variation in mean stress on fatigue life of CFRPs. From this point of view, therefore, Kawai et al. [5] have performed variable *R*-ratio fatigue tests on a quasi-isotropic woven fabric CFRP laminate in which the stress ratio of fatigue loading alternates between two different values under the condition that the maximum or minimum stress level is kept constant. From this study, it was found that fatigue life under the alternating *R*-ratio loading in which the stress ratio of fatigue loading alternates between two different values keeping the maximum level of fatigue stress at the same constant value is dominantly affected by fatigue loading at one of the two stress ratios under which fatigue life becomes shorter. The fatigue

Figure 1: Alternating R -ratio loading tests

lives predicted for alternating R -ratio loading using the Miner rule [6] agreed with the observed fatigue lives with an accuracy of a factor of two. This observation suggests that the Miner rule is satisfactory for prediction of fatigue life under alternation of the two waveforms of different R -ratios but of the same levels of maximum or minimum stresses.

Kawai and Ishizuka [7] have studied the second problem further, and examined fatigue life of the same composite laminate as in [5] under alternating R -ratio loading for different pairs of stress ratios, but at different constant values of fatigue life. By comparing the fatigue lives under constant and variable R -ratio loading conditions, they elucidated the influence of repeated alternation in R -ratio on fatigue life of the composite. It was demonstrated that a moderately conservative life of the composite under any alternating R -ratio loading can be predicted using the linear cumulative fatigue damage rule in conjunction with the anisomorphic constant fatigue life diagram by which the fatigue lives for the component constant amplitude loading waveforms involved can adequately be predicted.

In the present study, the variable R -ratio fatigue tests [7] in which the stress ratio of fatigue loading alternates between two specified values with different stress levels that correspond to the same number of cycles to failure are first reviewed. Then, a new methodology for predicting fatigue life of CFRPs under variable loading is developed. A variable maximum stress loading at a constant stress ratio that is equivalent to a given alternating R -ratio loading is identified. This assumption allows us to predict fatigue life for any given alternating R -ratio loading by applying the Miner rule to the constant stress ratio waveform identified. In order to validate this idea, fatigue tests are performed for the variable maximum stress loading waveforms at a constant stress ratio that are equivalent to the alternating R -ratio loading waveforms examined in the previous study.

2 MATERIAL AND TESTING PROCEDURE

2.1 Specimen

The material used in this study was a woven carbon/epoxy quasi-isotropic laminate $[(\pm 45)/(0/90)]_{4S}$ fabricated using a prepreg QFC133-6E01A (Toray). The cure temperature of laminates was 350°F (176.7°C). The thickness of laminates was about 3.2 mm. The experimental program in this study includes tension-compression and compression-compression fatigue loadings. For all the tests in this study, therefore, short specimens were used to reduce a risk of buckling during fatigue testing due to applied compressive stress. The dimensions of a short specimen are total length $L = 100$ mm, gauge

length $L_G = 10$ mm and width $W = 10$ mm. Rectangular-shaped aluminum-alloy tabs were glued on both ends of a specimen with epoxy adhesive in order to protect the gripped portions.

2.2 Test procedure

2.2.1 Constant R -ratio loading

The baseline constant R -ratio loading fatigue data that are required to determine the conditions of vertical and inclined alternating R -ratio loading tests have been obtained in the previous study [5] for five different constant values of stress ratio $R = 0.1, 0.5, 10, 2, -1$ and χ , respectively.

2.2.2 Vertical alternating R -ratio loading

In this variable loading test, as illustrated in Fig. 1(a), a block of two equal-life waveforms of different stress ratios R_1 and R_2 is repeatedly applied to a specimen until fatigue failure occurs. Note that in the vertical loading tests, $N_1^{(R_1)} = N_2^{(R_2)} = N_f^*$ and $\sigma_{\max}^{(R_1)} \neq \sigma_{\max}^{(R_2)}$. In the vertical (R_1, R_2) alternating R -ratio loading tests, it is assumed that R_1 takes a constant value equal to the critical stress ratio χ ($=\sigma_c / \sigma_T < 0$) of the composite tested, and the critical stress ratio is alternated with a different constant value of stress ratio $R_2 = 0.1, 0.5, 2$ and 10 , respectively. The waveforms of two different stress ratios $R_1 = \chi$ and $R_2 = R$ are combined together, half cycle for each, to form a cycle of new waveform, and it is repeated until fatigue failure occurs.

2.2.3 Inclined alternating R -ratio loading

In another variable loading test, as illustrated in Fig. 1(b), a block of two unequal-life and unequal-max-stress waveforms of different stress ratios R_1 and R_2 is repeatedly applied to a specimen until fatigue failure occurs. The inclined loading tests satisfy the conditions $N_1^{(R_1)} \neq N_2^{(R_2)}$ and $\sigma_{\max}^{(R_1)} \neq \sigma_{\max}^{(R_2)}$. The inclined alternating R -ratio loading tests are performed for four different pairs of stress ratios $(R_1, R_2) = (\chi, R) = (\chi, 0.1), (\chi, 0.5), (\chi, 10)$ and $(\chi, 2)$, respectively.

Figure 2: Results of vertical alternating R -ratio loading tests.

3 RESULTS OF VARIABLE LOADING FATIGUE TESTS

3.1 Fatigue life under vertical alternating R -ratio loading

Before going into development of a model in this study, let us first review the experimental results obtained by Kawai and Ishizuka [7]. Fig. 2 presents the log-log plots of the fatigue lives observed in the vertical alternating R -ratio loading tests against the fatigue lives predicted using the Miner rule with the constant R -ratio loading lives for the two original waveforms of different stress ratios that are

sequenced in a block. The dashed lines in Fig. 2 indicate the range of correlation of a factor of two. From Fig. 2, it is seen that all the fatigue life data obtained from the vertical alternating R -ratio loading fatigue tests are distributed outside the range of a factor of two, and they are distributed in the range of fatigue life from 1/2 to 1/1000 of the fatigue life predicted using the Miner rule. The results in Fig. 2 demonstrate not only that the use of the Miner rule with the fatigue lives for the original waveforms sequenced in a block of vertical alternating R -ratio loading does not allow predicting the vertical alternating R -ratio loading fatigue life with the accuracy of a factor of 2 that is favorable in engineering fatigue life prediction, but also that it gives significantly optimistic prediction of fatigue life under vertical alternating R -ratio loading.

3.2 Fatigue life under inclined alternating R -ratio loading

Under the inclined alternating R -ratio loading tests, two unequal-life waveforms of different stress ratios, $(R_1, \sigma_{\max}^{(R_1)}, N_{f1}^{(R_1)})$ and $(R_2, \sigma_{\max}^{(R_2)}, N_{f2}^{(R_2)})$, are alternately repeated until fatigue failure occurs. The inclined alternating R -ratio loading may be interpreted as proportional combination of vertical and horizontal alternating R -ratio loadings. Four kinds of inclined alternating R -ratio loading tests were carried out for each of the four different pairs of stress ratios $(R_1, R_2) = (\chi, 0.1)$, $(\chi, 0.5)$, $(\chi, 10)$ and $(\chi, 2)$. All the inclined loading test results are plotted in Fig. 3 against the predicted lives using the Miner rule in a manner similar to Fig. 2.

From Fig. 3, it is seen that the fatigue life data from the inclined alternating R -ratio loading tests are distributed a bit more closely to the band of a factor of two, but they are still outside the band, compared with the fatigue life data obtained from the vertical alternating R -ratio loading tests. This observation suggests that the component of horizontal alternating R -ratio loading involved by the inclined alternating R -ratio loading has an influence of reducing the deviation of the Miner sum at failure from the value of unity.

Figure 3: Results of inclined alternating R -ratio loading tests.

4 EQUIVALENT CONSTANT R -RATIO WAVEFORM METHOD

To achieve better prediction of fatigue life for variable R -ratio loading, we propose an equivalent constant R -ratio waveform method. In the proposed fatigue life prediction methodology, a given alternating R -ratio loading is replaced with an equivalent variable maximum stress loading at a constant stress ratio, as schematically illustrated in Fig. 4.

The proposed equivalent constant R -ratio waveform method assumes that the constant stress ratio of equivalent fatigue loading is identified with the critical stress ratio [3, 4]. Fatigue life for any variable amplitude at a constant stress ratio can approximately be predicted using the Miner rule [6]. This observation suggests that fatigue life for any equivalent variable amplitude loading at a constant

Figure 4: Equivalent variable amplitude loading at the critical stress ratio.

R -ratio can be predicted by direct application of the Miner rule. Note that the proposed equivalent constant R -ratio waveform method requires only the S-N relationship for constant amplitude loading at the critical stress ratio.

The predictions using the proposed equivalent constant R -ratio loading approach are shown in Fig. 5. In Fig. 5, we can see that the alternating R -ratio loading fatigue lives predicted using the proposed methodology are close to half the observed fatigue lives or even moderately shorter than the observed fatigue lives, regardless of the kind of alternation of waveforms of different stress ratios. The accuracy of prediction of fatigue life using this new methodology is thus much better than the accuracy of prediction in Fig. 2 that shows the results obtained by applying the Miner rule to the original waveforms sequenced in the vertical alternating R -ratio loading tests.

Figure 5: Predicted fatigue life for vertical alternating R -ratio loading using the equivalent waveform method.

The equivalent constant R -ratio waveform method is also applied to predict the fatigue life for inclined alternating R -ratio loading. The predicted fatigue is shown in Fig. 6. The proposed method allows us to conservatively predict the variable R -ratio loading fatigue life for any inclined loading with a simultaneous change in stress level and stress ratio, demonstrating a dramatic improvement in fatigue life prediction from an engineering point of view, compared with the results in Fig. 3 that were obtained using the Miner rule.

Figure 6: Predicted fatigue life for inclined alternating R -ratio loading using the equivalent waveform method.

5 EQUIVALENT CONSTANT FATIGUE STRESS METHOD

In the proposed equivalent constant R -ratio waveform method, a variable loading fatigue life is predicted using the S-N relationship for the critical stress ratio in conjunction with the Miner rule. The use of the Miner rule is necessary in this method since the equivalent waveform identified is still variable loading at a constant stress ratio.

From a different point of view, a further simplification may be achieved by adopting a concept of equivalent constant stress for fatigue. In contrast to the case for metals that rely on the S-N relationship for a symmetric alternating tension-compression loading at $R = -1$, we assume that the S-N relationship for the tension-compression loading at the critical stress ratio is identified with the reference S-N relationship from which an equivalent stress is obtained.

The S-N curve for the critical stress ratio can be written in the form

$$g_{\chi}(\sigma_{\max})N_f^{(\chi)} = C \quad (1)$$

where g_{χ} is a nonlinear function for loading at the critical stress ratio. In place of consideration of any interaction between the waveforms involved by variable loading, the damage per cycle for each constituent waveform involved is replaced with that for the critical stress ratio as

$$D^*(\sigma_{\max}) = \frac{1}{N_f^{(\chi)}} = \frac{g_{\chi}(\sigma_{\max})}{C} \quad (2)$$

This assumption conservatively counts the effect of damage accumulation. Substitution of Eq. (2) in the Miner rule yields

$$\sum n_i D^*(\sigma_{\max}^{(i)}) = \sum \frac{n_i}{N_f^{(\chi)}(\sigma_{\max}^{(i)})} = \frac{1}{C} \sum n_i g_{\chi}(\sigma_{\max}^{(i)}) = 1 \quad (3)$$

Using Eq. (1) and Eq. (3), we can define an equivalent stress for loading at the critical stress ratio as

$$\bar{\sigma}_{\max}^{(\lambda)} = g^{-1} \left(\frac{\sum n_i g_{\lambda}(\sigma_{\max}^{(i)})}{\sum n_i} \right) \quad (4)$$

Note that the equivalent stress for fatigue is associated with loading at the critical stress ratio. The fatigue life for variable loading is then calculated by substituting Eq. (4) in Eq. (1). If the reference S-N curve can be described by means of the Basquin law, then Eq. (4) can be written in the form

$$\bar{\sigma}_{\max}^{(\lambda)} = \left(\frac{\sum n_i (\sigma_{\max}^{(i)})^b}{\sum n_i} \right)^{1/b} \quad (5)$$

The correlation between the fatigue life predicted using the equivalent constant fatigue stress for the critical stress ratio and the experimental results was similar to that shown in Fig. 5 for the vertical alternating *R*-ratio loading and in Fig. 6 for the inclined alternating *R*-ratio loading.

6 CONCLUSIONS

In the present study, the influence of repeated change in stress ratio on fatigue life of woven CFRP quasi-isotropic laminate has been discussed. Two kinds of alternating *R*-ratio loading tests were first reviewed to clarify the effect of variation in stress ratio on fatigue life of composites and to define the problem to be tackled with in this study. These experimental results demonstrate that a significantly optimistic prediction of fatigue life is achieved by the Miner rule for both the vertical and inclined alternating *R*-ratio loadings. In order to obtain better prediction of fatigue life, which is preferably conservative from an engineering point of view, development of a new fatigue life prediction method has been attempted. In the proposed method, the variable amplitude loading at a constant *R*-ratio that is equivalent to a given more complicated variable loading involving different *R*-ratios is first identified, and the fatigue lives for the waveforms that constitute the equivalent waveform identified using the S-N relationship for the representative stress ratio and they are substituted in the Miner rule to predict the fatigue life for the variable loading of interest. The proposed equivalent constant *R*-ratio waveform method allows moderately conservative prediction of fatigue life for all the different vertical and inclined alternating *R*-ratio loadings tested in this study. Additionally, we have developed another method called an equivalent stress method in the form suitable for composites. It is characteristic that the effective stress is defined with reference to fatigue loading of a given composite at the critical stress ratio. The prediction of fatigue life predicted using the equivalent stress method was found to be comparable to that using the equivalent constant *R*-ratio waveform method.

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